

ISSN 2455-393X

Journal of the English Literator Society

Volume 11 Issue 5 September 2025 | www.jels.in

Research Article

Spiritual Rebirth of Ahalya with Reference to Kavita Kane's *Ahalya's Awakening*

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Published online: 30 September 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17235858>

ABSTRACT

Kavita Kane, an inspiring writer, prefers the themes of the great epics, and her choice of characters edges on the mythological characters who are least celebrated and remain as the minor characters without much limelight. Her novels have achieved a stupendous transition among the reading audience as the novels educate, captivate, and inspire the readers, and provide an extensive insight regarding the representation of the characters. Through *Ahalya's Awakening*, Kavita Kane acknowledges women's courage, prudence, resilience, and strength with regard to the characterization of myriad characters. The character traits of Ahalya have a contemporary relevance to the identity of women of recent times, as the novel throws light on the choices and decisions of Ahalya, which have doomed her fate. Books like *Sita's Sister*, *Karna's Wife*, and *Ahalya's Awakening* indeed provide a glimpse of the minor women characters of the epic, and such novels intrinsically trace the complete characteristic attributes right from their birth to the last phase of their lives.

KEYWORDS: Empowerment; Mythology; Resilience; Spiritual Awakening; Transition

FULL PAPER

The story actually begins with the story of Indra Nahusha who had lecherous eye on Sachi, wife of the previous Indra Shakra who himself was the reason for his tragic flaw “The king of gods chased a married woman—that was his downfall. He lost it all; his virility, his looks, his kingdom, this throne...” (Kane 1). The rishi Brihaspathi admonished Indra for his unethical intention and reprimanded him that the position of Indra is just a temporary title based on conduct, karma, and punya. Menaka reminded Indra Nahusha that Shakra faced the downfall as he had involved himself in committing adultery with a married woman. Further, Menaka narrated the story of Ahalya, her husband Gowtham, and Indra Shakra to explicate the tragic plot that eventually made the three prime characters suffer in their lives.

Ahalya has a passion for learning and is inquisitive about diverse things, whatever she observes in her life. Like Sita’s Sister, Urmila, Ahalya was also blessed with intellectual freedom and celebrated as a renowned scholar of her time. Her name, ‘Ahalya’, eventually suggests that she was born as an unblemished woman without any physical deformity. She was reluctant to marry anyone, as her passion was absolutely in pursuing scholarly learning from the prominent gurus of her time. She was resolute with unflinching determination about her becoming a Rishika to quench her thirst for knowledge like King Ulysses. Right from her childhood, she had always taken extraordinary steps out of the way to prove herself when she was resisted or discouraged from accomplishing it.

When the marriage proposal knocked on her door in the name of Indra, a good friend and a confidant of her brother, Divodas, she boldly asserted to her parents about her passion for learning and disinterest in marriage. Ahalya is the perfect blend of beauty and brain, and nowhere in her life had she ever bragged about her standard of living. Even the *devas* and *apsaras* were quite jealous of her immaculate beauty and the divine aura that radiated from her feminine charm. “Ahalya was the most beautiful woman on earth and in the three heavens” (Kane 5). Ahalya and Divodas were born as twins, and both brother and sister are blessed to have been born to the parents, the king Mudgal and the queen Nalayani. Her father once admired the name Ahalya, which means that the real meaning of her name is something related to the earth or the soil. “Ahalya means the plough, too, when broken into two parts—a a-halya, as related to ploughing.” (Kane 8). Both siblings shared the perspicacity to understand things and to learn anything new. As the guru Vashisht himself had once praised Ahalya for holding great willpower and fascination towards a lot of things in her life. Once when she was practicing archery, all of a sudden, she went missing as she ran to the specific spot in order to find the whereabouts of the arrow. In fact, Divodas is lovable, caring,

and always had a great understanding of her sister and remained as her absolute moral strength.

When things were going unperturbed, destiny had a twist in her life in the name of 'Indra', who was passionately in love with Ahalya. Though Indra was handsome and alluring, Ahalya's intention was in education and not to settle down in marital life. She had never wanted her life to be some "cloistered princess who just looks pretty and does nothing!" (Kane 22). She was valiant in her strong rebukes at Indra whenever she was approached for marriage, and she was dauntless when he was questioned whether their marriage had to be arranged in turn for his timely help to his brother, Divodas, in waging a war against Shambar. With the impending war, Ahalya's family decided to send her to the *Ashram* of Rishi Gautam, the favourite of Lord Brahma, who had acquired a wide reputation for his prolific learning. He was "an expert on law, especially women's laws, and is constructing the Nyay Sutras for them as well." (Kane 58). Being a sharp-witted person, Ahalya had her own doubts about the sudden transformation in her mother's decision to send her to pursue her dream.

Ahalya developed a great affinity towards Uttank, the favourite disciple of Rishi Gautam. When Rishi Gautam informed Ahalya about the impending war in her kingdom and informed her about the reason for her stay in the *ashram*, she was in complete remorse and was absolutely perplexed. She was happy and relaxed with the companionship of Gautam when he wiped all her grief with a moment of conversation and revelation. Rishi Vashisht had already validated Ahalya to Gautam as a savant, as he always felt proud and content at the sagacity of Ahalya.

The presence of Ahalya in the ashram had created a pleasant ambience for the inmates of the place as she transformed it with her divine aura, and the place had no garden before her arrival. "The barren expanses had transformed into blossoming shrubbery; flowers and bushes and grass replaced the bare ground." Further, she "changed the kitchen into a warm, hearty space, filled with the simple flavors of turmeric and the aroma of wholesome, tasty food." (Kane 81). Ahalya had a sharp mind and quick wit, and she showered compassion on each and every being on the earth. Gautam wondered about how her happiness is absolutely contagious as she develops a cordial relationship with everyone around her. She had dedicated herself totally to learning, and she was instantaneous in grasping. This quality astounded Gautam at the sagacity of Ahalya.

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aroma of wholesome, tasty food.”(Kane 81). Ahalya had a sharp mind and quick wit, and she showered compassion on each and every being on the earth. Gautam wondered about how her happiness is absolutely contagious as she develops a cordial relationship with everyone around her. She had dedicated herself totally to learning, and she was instantaneous in grasping, and Gautam was totally astounded at the sagacity of Ahalya. Kavita Kane’s *Sita’s Sister* embarks on the storyline where Urmila, Sita’s sister, is given a new dimension, where she was always overshadowed by Sita throughout her life. Her individuality was never lauded and celebrated, unlike the popular character, Sita.

Kavita Kane, in her phenomenal revisionist interpretation, has projected *Karna’s wife* as having projected the feminist journey beyond several challenges in the quest for her identity in a patriarchal society. The epics *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* have remained as the main subjects of interpretations and re-interpretations of myriad characters. In these epics, the characterization of heroes was glorified and made central to the narratives, whereas women characters were largely ignored and neglected in the mainstream of narration. The novels of Kavita Kane explore such marginalized and peripheral characters to shower them with the limelight to indicate their struggle for existence in the dominant society of men. Through this novel, she enunciates the epic from Uruvi’s perspective by recounting her side of the story, where she was a fictitious character created by Kavita Kane. The novel focuses on the perspective of Uruvi, who lived as the faithful wife of Karna, who was an outcaste and socially secluded for being born in the lowest strata of society.

Unlike other princesses, Uruvi, a strong and independent girl, acted on her free will without any restrictions from his father. She was adept at riding horses and climbing trees, and in addition, Rishi Bangola introduced her to new windows of learning Ayurveda and healing. Her father, King Vahusha, was fascinated to find Uruvi, a sensitive woman nursing the bloodied bodies of the wounded soldiers of the war. Similarly, in *Ahalya’s Awakening*, the valiant Ahalya, a royal princess, married the rishi Gautam and sacrificed her happiness and dream only to live under his protection and love. Just like the father of Ahalya, who had fervently supported the choices of Ahalya in every walk of life, in this novel, Vahusha stands firmly at the side of his daughter, Uruvi, when she decides to marry an outcaste. Uruvi lived her life under the looming shadow, and just like Urmila, *Sita’s sister*, she always showers love and compassion on everyone around her. She walked away from Karna when he was one of the others to humiliate Draupadi in the royal court. She stood her ground to support Draupadi for the humiliation that she faced and confronted Karna with righteous fury for his injustice. Despite the problems and humiliations that she faced in every facet of life, Uruvi and Urmila established themselves as the compassionate women who were instantaneous in exhibiting their love and concern towards everyone, even the prime

reason for the whirlpool of problems in the usual current of their lives. Though women were born and raised as brave, their powers were absolutely thwarted by men warriors and mighty kings who dominated the world with a set of standards and doctrines.

Gita Hariharan's *Thousand Faces of Night* explicates the minor women characters who were forsaken of their social status in the epics through the narration of the grandmother of Devi. Amba, the minor character, was not shown justice by the mighty warrior, Bheeshma, when he had brought Amba by force to his kingdom, and to her surprise, she was rejected by Salwa. Bheeshma had also rejected the proposal of Amba when she approached him to marry her. Therefore, Amba was penanced to Lord Shiva and had received the boon to kill Bheeshma in her next birth. In the next birth, she was born as the daughter of Drupada of Panchala and raised as a son in the name of Shikhandi, and finally, took her chance to take revenge against Bheeshma.

Kavita Kane's intention to choose this particular character was that she wanted to unveil the contradictory ideas associated with *Panchakanyakas*. She questioned everyone that if ever Ahalya was cursed for her infidelity, then why had she been added as the first woman in the list of *Panchakanyakas*. In every other story, Ahalya was made passive, and she was never given a voice to advocate for her suffering. All these reasons ignited the mind of Kavita Kane to represent the true voice of Ahalya, where she was given a chance to advocate for her miseries and show the world her real power. If Ahalya had to be accused, then Gautam holds an equal responsibility for the fate of their lives. The writer always prefers to choose the minor characters from the epics who were absolutely neglected and marginalized from the mainstream of narration.

Works cited

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